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Review Article

**JAUNDICE: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF CAUSES,
CONSEQUENCES AND TREATMENT.****Miss.Chinnabathini Rushmitha, Mrs. K.Naveen Kumari, Dr.k.Venu Gopal.**¹Final Year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy college, Tirupati -517506.²Associate professor, Department of pharmacology, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati - 517506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati -517506.**Abstract:**

A medical illness known as jaundice, or icterus, is characterized by yellowish colouring of the skin, mucous membranes, and eyes as a result of high blood bilirubin levels. Normal bilirubin levels are less than 1.0 mg/dL; when levels rise above 3 mg/dL, jaundice becomes clinically noticeable. Haemolysis is the main cause of prehepatic jaundice, while liver disorders and dysfunctions induce hepatic jaundice. This condition can have prehepatic, hepatic, or post hepatic origins. Bile duct blockages, such as gallstones or tumours, cause post hepatic jaundice. Changes in bilirubin metabolism are the underlying pathophysiology, which is frequently associated with haemolytic anaemia, liver disease, or obstruction of bile flow. Laboratory testing, imaging studies, and physical examinations are frequently used in the diagnosis process. Depending on the kind of jaundice, several treatment approaches are used, such as immunoglobulin infusion, antiviral drugs, dietary modifications, and phototherapy, especially in newborns. For efficient management and better patient outcomes, it is essential to comprehend the many causes and therapies of jaundice.

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INTRODUCTION:

Jaundice is also known as icterus. The word Jaundice is actually a derivative of French word 'Jaune' which means 'yellow'(1). It is defined as a medical condition characterized by a yellowish discoloration of the skin, eye and mucus membrane due to an accumulation of high bilirubin level in the blood. Jaundice is the most common of all liver problems of the mucous membrane and the yellow color of skin because of increase in the bilirubin, bile pigment in the blood. Normal level of bilirubin in blood are below 1.0mg/dl. When serum bilirubin level exceeds 3 mg /dL, jaundice becomes clinically apparent and the jaundice varies depending on the underlying cause, and it is more common in certain age groups. Namely, jaundice affects approximately 6 out of 10 otherwise healthy newborns(2). The 3.8mg/ kg bilirubin is produced daily in normal adult. The production of bilirubin in neonates is much higher than the adult(3). Jaundice in adults rare while jaundice in babies common with an estimated 80 % affected during their first week of lifetime(4). Jaundice can also caused by other diseases like hepatitis, or gallstones, malaria.(5)

High blood bilirubin is divided into two forms

1. Unconjugated bilirubin: High unconjugated bilirubin may be due to excess red blood cell break down, not eating for prolonged period of time, large bruises, thyroid problems and genetic conditions such as Gilberts syndrome

2. conjugated bilirubin: High conjugated bilirubin may be due to liver disease such as infection, blockage of bile duct, hepatitis, gall stones, cancer

PREHEPATIC JAUNDICE:

Prehepatic jaundice occurs when there is an excess of bilirubin synthesis that occur before it reaches the liver for processing. This is frequently caused by hemolysis, where red blood cells are degraded at an increased serum bilirubin level.

CAUSES

1. Hemolytic Anemia: Disorders like sickle cell anemia, thalassemia, or autoimmune hemolytic anemia.
2. Blood Transfusion Reactions: Incompatible blood transfusions can lead to rapid hemolysis
3. Certain Infections: Some infections can increase red blood cell destruction.
4. Genetic Disorders: Conditions like Gilbert's syndrome or Crigler-Najjar syndrome affect bilirubin metabolism.

Symptoms

1. Yellowing of skin and eyes (icterus)
2. Pale stools
3. Fatigue
4. Abdominal pain (possibly)
5. Splenomegaly (enlarged spleen, in some cases)

These symptoms arise due to elevated levels of unconjugated bilirubin in the bloodstream. If you suspect jaundice, it's important to consult a healthcare provider for a proper evaluation.

Properties: Elevated Indirect (Unconjugated) Bilirubin Levels

characteristic:

1. Increased bilirubin production (e.g., hemolysis)
2. Decreased hepatic uptake of bilirubin
3. Impaired bilirubin conjugation

Range:

- Normal range: 0.2-0.8 mg/dL
- Pre-hepatic jaundice range: >2 mg/dL

HEPATIC JAUNDICE

Hepatic jaundice, also called as hepatocellular jaundice, it occurs when the liver is injured or less functional, impairing it become a more difficult to metabolize bilirubin. This build up to an accumulation of bilirubin in the bloodstream, resulting in yellowing of the skin and eyes.

CAUSES

1. Liver diseases: Hepatitis (viral, alcoholic), cirrhosis, liver cancer.
2. Toxins: Alcohol, certain medications, or substances.
3. Genetic disorders: Conditions like Gilbert's syndrome.

Symptoms

1. Yellowing of the skin and eyes (icterus)
2. Dark urine (due to increased bilirubin)
3. Pale stools (indicating bile obstruction)
4. Itching (pruritus)
5. Fatigue and weakness
6. Abdominal pain or discomfort, especially in the upper right quadrant
7. Nausea and vomiting

Properties: Elevated Conjugated (Direct) Bilirubin Levels

characteristic:

1. Impaired bilirubin conjugation
2. Decreased bile flow
3. Hepatocellular damage or dysfunction

Range:

Normal Range: Conjugated (direct) bilirubin: 0-0.4 mg/dL

Hepatic Jaundice Range: Conjugated (direct) bilirubin: >0.5 mg/dL (typically 2-10 mg/dL)

POST HEPATIC JAUNDICE

Post hepatic jaundice is also known as obstructive jaundice(6), it occur when there is a blockage in the bile duct, bile cannot drain from the liver into the intestine. This leads to an accumulation of bile and bilirubin in the liver and blood steam resulting jaundice.

Post hepatic jaundice occlusion of the bile duct obstruction due to choledocholithiasis, diseases of the bile duct such as malignant, inflammatory and compression of outside bile duct(7)

CAUSES

1. Gallstones: Commonly block the common bile duct.
2. Tumors: Pancreatic or biliary tumors can compress or invade bile ducts.
3. Strictures: Narrowing of bile ducts due to inflammation or scarring.
4. Pancreatitis: Inflammation of the pancreas may cause duct obstruction.

Symptoms

1. Yellowing of the skin and eyes (jaundice)
2. Dark urine
3. Pale or clay-colored stools
4. Itchy skin
5. Abdominal pain (especially in the right upper quadrant)
6. Nausea and vomiting
7. Loss of appetite
8. Weight loss

Properties: Elevated Conjugated (Direct) Bilirubin due to bile duct obstruction

Characteristic

1. Bile duct obstruction
2. Impaired bile flow
3. Cholestasis (bile flow stagnation)

Range:

1. Conjugated bilirubin > 80% of total bilirubin
2. Bilirubin levels > 2 mg/dL

METABOLISM OF BILIRUBIN AND PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF JAUNDICE

Degradation of heme is accountable for bilirubin formation. Heme and globin are separated from free hemoglobin by macrophage phagocytosis. The bilirubin formation occurs in two steps.

In 1st step: the microsomal enzyme heme oxygenase catalyses which yields biliverdin, iron, & carbon oxide.

In 2nd step: biliverdin reductase, a cytosolic enzyme, subsequently produces unconjugated bilirubin(8). The unconjugated bilirubin subsequently circulates via the blood to the liver. This bilirubin is carried through the blood attached to serum albumin because it is water insoluble. The unconjugated bilirubin converted to

bilirubin diglucuronide (Conjugated bilirubin) by the liver enzyme UDP-glucuronyl transferase. The conjugated bilirubin from liver cells is discharged via bile and into the gall bladder. The bilirubin enters the digestive system. In the intestine, the intestinal cells predominantly absorb conjugated bilirubin, which is later transformed into urobilinogen. While the unabsorbed part of urobilinogen undergoes change into stercobilinogen and subsequently oxidation to become stercobilin. The material that stercobilin excrete in its feces. The urobilinogen is reabsorbed into the cells of the digestive tract. The hepatobiliary recirculation occurs, then the kidney filters a lower amount of reabsorbed urobilinogen and it is converted into urobilin in the urine. The results of an alteration of bilirubin metabolism leads to jaundice(9).

CAUSES:

Hemolytic Jaundice

Hemolytic Jaundice is occurred when there is over production of bilirubin by the excessive break down of Red blood cell

There are two major sites of hemolysis

Intravascular hemolysis

The red blood cells degraded in blood vessels within the vasculature, and allowing to hemoglobin is released and to form a haptoglobin- hemoglobin complexes with a haptoglobin, these complexes are break down by the spleen and hepatocytosis. The hemolysis is abnormally more, and the unbound hemoglobin is changed into methemoglobin from which heme is bind to haptoglobin or plasma albumin it easily facilitates removal. when the haptoglobin is depleted, the free hemoglobin is filtered by the kidney it leads produce the hemoglobinuria and tubular damage. additionally, degradation of hemoglobin causes increase the level of bilirubin which leads to jaundice

Extravascular hemolysis

The red blood cell is break down by the Macrophages in the reticuloendothelial system and this process when the antibodies bind to RBC for degradation(10).

As the cell of phagocytes are destructed hemoglobin into heme and globin and Breakdown heme metabolized into bilirubin for conjugation eventually eliminated through bile which leads to increases indirect bilirubin and to causes Jaundice

DIAGNOSIS:

- Jaundice Eye Colour Index (JECI):**
 Jaundice Eye Colour Index (JECI) with the digital photography of the sclera, where a JECI of 0 it produce a white colour, and a JECI of 0.1 it produce a yellow colour, which provide sign of hemolytic jaundice(11).
- complete blood count (CBC) testing:**
 complete blood count (CBC) testing used for the determination for total serum bilirubin
- Bilirubin blood test**
 This test is used identify the level of bilirubin in the blood and help determine the jaundice
- Urine test**
 This help to determine the presence conjugated hyper bilirubinemia
- A Coomb's test**
 A Coomb's test should be conducted, and end-tidal carbon monoxide concentration

should be used to maintain the rate of hemolytic

- **Red blood cell distribution width (RDW)** study Used to measure the anisocytes

TREATMENT

- **Phototherapy:** Special blue lights used for the baby's body get rid of more bilirubin.
- **Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG):** A fluid that contains antibodies from donors used to maintain the baby's red blood cells.
- **Intravenous fluids:** maintain the baby stay hydrated and get rid of more bilirubin

Gilbert's syndrome

Gilbert's syndrome is a mild hyperbilirubinemia because of the defect in bilirubin metabolism. UGT1A1 gene is involves mutation .and UDP-glucuronosyl-transferase 1 family of polypeptide A1 enzyme (UGT1A1). UGT1A1 enzyme catalyzes the responsible for unconjugated bilirubin to conjugated bilirubin by ester linkage of the propionic acid side chains of bilirubin with glucuronic acid, which is presence of uridine diphosphate-glucuronic acids(12). This process leads to the formation of diglucuronide conjugate. uridine diphosphate (UDP)-glucuronosyltransferase which is present in the liver(13).

The main function of this UGT1A1 is mainly for the accumulation of unconjugated bilirubin leads to produce Jaundice especially during the dehydration, and fasting and this unconjugated bilirubin is excreted through bile. Therefore, any variations in the UGT1A1 gene may decrease its activity and leading to Unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia. UGT1A1 gene is associated with mild unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia which is Gilbert's syndrome

DIAGNOSIS (14)

Unconjugated Hyperbilirubinemia

- **Higher bilirubin production:** extravascular and intravascular hemolysis, liver diseases, Wilson's disease resorbing hematoma.
- **Hemolytic disorder:** Sickle cell anemia, G6PD deficiency
- **Compromised hepatic bilirubin uptake:** heart failure, portosystemic shunts
- **Advanced cirrhosis:** This can cause impaired bilirubin conjugation
- **Hyperthyroidism:** It produces impaired bilirubin conjugation
- **Weakened bilirubin conjugation:** Crigler-Najjar syndrome types I and II The high altitude living, dyserythropoiesis, ethinyl

estradiol and thyrotoxicosis are consideration

Conjugated Hyperbilirubinemia

- **Failure of canalicular organic anion transport:** Dubin-Johnson syndrome crigler nijar syndrome
- **Environmental hepatotoxins:** Organic solvent, beryllium
- **Failure of sinusoidal reuptake of conjugated bilirubin:** Rotor syndrome.
- **Biliary obstruction:** Biliary atresia and obstruction of bile flow
- **Extrahepatic cholestasis:** choledocholithiasis, pancreaticobiliary malignancy, ,

Treatment

- Gilbert's syndrome is not necessary for the treatment, this is condition identified by mild, fluctuating elevations in bilirubin levels. Most individuals with Gilbert's syndrome produces a normal, healthy lives without any problems. It mainly focuses on the education about the Gilbert's syndrome . If there is a symptoms like fatigue or jaundice, it is necessary to consult a healthcare professional for proper treatment

Obstruction jaundice

In Obstructive jaundice the blockage of the Bile flow from the liver to the gall bladder and then reaching into the small intestine. Jaundice occurs due to raised either conjugated or unconjugated bilirubin .it is bases upon the metabolism change occur in bilirubin It is divided into three types

1. Pre hepatic

It is primarily form there is high amount of the bilirubin which is more the capability of the liver to conjugate the bilirubin and eliminate through the gut. There is a increase in the level of unconjugated bilirubin. The prehepatic cause is hemolytic anemia, during there is an large amounts of degraded heme and their common causes of Hemolytic disease in infants.

2. Intrahepatic

cause for hyperbilirubinemia is occur due two liver dysfunction and parenchymal liver disease, thereby liver inability to either eliminate the bilirubin or conjugated .this occur due the various disease like auto immune cirrhosis, alcoholic liver disease, viral Hepatitis.in this hepatic Jaundice the both unconjugated and conjugated components are increased , followed by the indirect component. Additionally liver enzyme level are increase the reflecting liver injury.

3. Post hepatic

It causes the obstruction of the bile flow which may leads to the blockage of the extrahepatic biliary moved between the liver and duodenum. It is commonly occur due to the pancreatic cancers, gall stones condition and it leads to the rises of conjugated bilirubin is known as Hyperbilirubinemia(15). and become decreases the bilirubin level in intestine This are observed in the obstructive jaundice.

DIAGNOSIS

- Haematological investigation are used for the determination of obstructive jaundice
- Hepatitis panel test are conduct for Diagnosis of obstruction of jaundice
- Gamma glutamy transpeptidase is used to evaluated bile duct obstruction
- Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma is caused the pancreatic cancer that can be identity by the endoscopic ultra sounds
- Resectable pancreatic cancers can be treated by the chemotherapy
- Serum transaminase are determine in cholangitis.their is not occur in the liver parenchymal disease
- Ultrasound is a preliminary used for the determine obstruction
- Endoscopic ultrasound is used for evaluation of malignant obstructive (16)
- MRCP is used for the determination of the biliary tract and preferred for imaging studying
- Radiotherapy is used for Diagnosis of cancer growth
- ERCP is used to evaluation of the preliminary imaging ptc is used as alternative fot ERCP
- Alkaline phosphate and carcinoembryonic antigen used for the Diagnosis of obstruction Jaundice (17)
- Gemcitabine and cisplatin is used for the evaluation of cholangiocarcinoma

TREATMENT

- **Endoscopic intervention**
It is used release the Obstruction of the bile or pancreatic ducts which are caused by the gall stones it released the stone by using ERCP
- **Surgical intervention**
Surgery are done because of the sevier condition of obstruction Cholecystectomy Whipple procedure Biliary bypass surgery
- **Radiotherapy**

It used for the Treatment for the Endoscopic procedures

- **Percutaneous biliary drainage**

If their is not occurs the surgery in immediately then inserting of of catheter into the skin to stop the bile.

Cholestasis

It is a condition characterized by reduce the flow of the bile, which can leads to build up the bile acids in the blood stream this caused due to the certain medication and liver disease

If the bilirubin is present the rbc then it is degraded and cholestasis causes raises the bilirubinlevel in the blood. When bilirubin more in normal level then it occur in the skin and eye leads to jaundice, which is a yellow colour of skin and eye and it reduce the bile salt elimination

Liver cirrhosis

Liver cirrhosis produce the Jaundice due to the impaired liver ability to produce bilirubin and degradation of red blood cells and excrete the bilirubin through the bile.in cirrhosis the Liver tissue are damaged and the bilirubin buildup in the blood stream. The more concentration of bilirubin it present in the mucous and skin and leads to formation of yellow of skin and eye and buildup Jaundice

It can also causes:

- Bile flow blockage it avoid the elimination through intestine
- The liver blood vessels pressure is increase the bilirubin forcefully transformed into systematic circulation
- Impaired Liver function leads to decrease the bilirubin conjugation and clearance it cause accumulation of bilirubin in blood

DIAGNOSIS

Physical examination

Physical examination is focused on the possible causes of jaundice and intra hepatic disorders such as viral hepatitis, drug induced liver injury, chronic liver disease, and alcoholic liver disease

The physical examination should be includes:

- Evaluation of abdomen or lymph nodes in the supraclavicular area are suggestive of malignancy causing obstructive jaundice
- Light colored stools and dark colored urine suggest an obstruction bile duct
- The abnormal collection of blood vessels near the surface of the skin, redness of palms , increased the breast tissue in men

- Stigmata of liver failure or portal hypertension such as caput medusa are suggestive of a chronic parenchymal liver disease
- Assessing for any signs of chronic liver disease including burising
- The presence of abdominal trauma raises a suspicion of Obstructive to the bile duct

Laboratory test

- Laboratory test used to identify the etiology of jaundice
- An elevated Glutamyl transferase level can be connected with biliary obstruction and hepatocellular damage
- There is elevation of alkaline phosphate depending upon the symptoms and severity of obstruction and parenchymal liver disease, but also connected with non biliary pathological process in kidney intestine
- To identify hemolysis and evaluate for anemia of chronic disease and thrombocytopenia

- Leukocytosis is more seen in infection and inflammation causes of obstruction

Imaging study

Diagnostic imaging provide additional information

Ultrasound

The gall bladder is evaluated using ultrasonography. The proximal extra hepatic bile duct and dilated intra hepatic bile duct can both be identifiable.

Ultrasound not visualize the distal extra hepatic and pancreas due to gas in duodenum further imaging is necessary to obtain for evaluation of pancreatic head, pancreatic duct.

Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography:

To identify the intra and extra hepatic biliary tree. This are visualize the biliary system and help to determine the level and possibly the cause of obstruction.

MEDICINAL PLANTS

Botanical name	Common name	family	Therapeutic uses	Adverse effects
1.Aloe barbadensis	Aloe vera	liliaceae	Skin care Anti inflammatory wound healing	Gastrointestinal upset Allergic reaction
2.Anethum graveolens	Dill	Apiaceae	Flavouring agent Skin,hairproducts	Phototoxicity Infant harm
3.Abrus precatorius	Gurivinda	Fabaceae	Rheumatism Antimicrobial	Respiratory failure Abdominal pain
4.Bambusa vulgaris	Bamboo	Poaceae	Fever reduction Antimicrobial	Contact dermatitis Rhinitis
5.Betula utilize	Himalaya brich	Birch	Antiseptic Diuretic	Nausea Allergic reactions
6.Bryophyllum pinnatum	Cathedral bells	Crassulaceae	Menstrual issues Wound healing	Hypersensitive Diabetes
7.Citrus paradisi	Grape fruit	Rutaceae	Cholesterol reduction	Potential harm to fetus
8.Cassia angustifolia	Indian senna	Fabaceae	Laxative treat bowel obstruction	Hypokalemia Electrolyte imbalance

9. <i>Curcuma angustifolia</i>	Narrow leaved turmeric	Zingiberaceae	Diarrhea Antioxidant	Vomiting Skin rashes
10. <i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Chicory	Asteraceae	Liver and gall bladder problems	Respiratory issues
11. <i>Calotropis procera</i>	Milk weed	Apocynaceae	Hypertension Insecticidal and pesticidal properties	Hepatotoxicity Nephrotoxicity
12. <i>Embllica officialis</i>	Gooseberry	Euphorbiaceae	Skin care Neuroprotectivity	Hypersensitivity to vitamin c
13. <i>Euphoria hirta</i>	Asthma plant	Euphorbiaceae	Asthma Dysentery	Respiratory issues Skin irritation
14. <i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel	Apiaceae	Anti inflammatory and Antioxidant Properties	Gastrointestinal upset
15. <i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Peepal tree	Moraceae	Constipation Asthma	Wheezing Nausea
16. <i>hippophae tibetana</i>	Sand thorn	Elaegnaceae	Antioxidant Cough	Blood thinners Diabetes
17. <i>Inula helenium</i>	Elecampane	Asteraceae	Antimicrobial Properties Bronchitis	Nausea Diarrhea
18. <i>Juniperus communis</i>	Juniper	Cupressaceae	Digestive issues	Kidney problems
19. <i>Justica adhatoda</i>	Malabar nut	Acenthaceae	Cough Wound healing	Cough Wheezing
20. <i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	Linseed	Linaceae	Nutritional supplement	Thyroid problems
21. <i>Leucas cephalotus</i>	Spider nut	Lamiaceae	Anti-inflammatory Rheumatism	Eye irritation Skin irritation
22. <i>Morinda citrifolia</i>	Noni	Rubiaceae	Pain relief Immune system support	Potential uterine stimulation
23. <i>Mentha arvensis</i>	Pudina	Lamiaceae	Mouth ulcer Anxiety	Liver damage
24. <i>Myristica fragrans</i>	Nutmeg	Myristicaceae	Ayurvedic and unani medicines	Psychosis during High dose
25. <i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Drumstick	Moringaceae	Antioxidant Coagulant Properties	Nausea Skin irritation
26. <i>Olea europaea</i>	Olive	Oleaceae	Skin and hair care	Lower Bloodpressure
27. <i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	Indian caper	Bignoniaceae	Anxiety Fever reduction	Respiratory issues
28. <i>Phyllanthus niruri</i>	Shatter stone	Euphorbiaceae	Urinary track infection	Itching Skin rashes
29. <i>Plantago ovata</i>	Psyllium	Plantaginaceae	Laxative and fiber supplement	Diarrhea
30. <i>Pistacia integerrmia</i>	Kakra sindhi	Anacardiaceae	Cough Asthma	Skin irritation

31. <i>Rheum emodi</i>	Rhubarb	Polygonaceae	Laxative	Stomach cramps
32. <i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Radish	Brassicaceae	Lowering the blood pressure and cholesterol	Stomach irritation Gallstone blockage
33. <i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	Indian madder	Rubiaceae	Natural dye	Urine discoloration
34. <i>Spharanthus indicus</i>	East Indian globe thistle	Asteraceae	Eczema Diarrhea	Neuroleptic
35. <i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Costus	Asteraceae	Hepatoprotective Gout	Hypokalemia
36. <i>Sambucus nigra</i>	Elder berry	Adoxaceae	Antiviral Properties	Cyanide toxicity
37. <i>Scorzonera divaricate</i>	Vipers herb	Asteraceae	Jaundice Wound healing	Nephrotoxicity
38. <i>Tylophora indica</i>	Ananthamool	Asclepiadaceae	Antileptic Antiarthritic	Nausea Vomiting
39. <i>Taxacum officinalies</i>	Dandelion	Asteraceae	Laxatives Constipation	Stomach discomfort Increase bleeding
40. <i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Glubel	menispermaceae	Antileptotic Antispasmodic	Redness Stomach discomfort
41. <i>Tamarindus indica linn</i>	Tamarind	Fabaceae	Flavouring agent Souring agent	Heart burn Allergic reactions
42. <i>Vernonia anthelmintic</i>	Purple fleabane	Asteraceae	Parasite infection	Abdominal cramps Drowsiness
43. <i>Vinca rosea</i>	catharanthus	Apocynaceae	Antihypertensive	Liver damage Low blood pressure
44. <i>Uvaria urceu</i>	Prishniparni	Annonaceae	It balance the dosha	Cardiac arrhythmias
45. <i>Uraria picta</i>	Dabra	Leguminosae	Healingbone fracture	Seizures Nephrotoxicity Electrolyte imbalance
46. <i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>	Shiranjji tea	Lithraceae	jaundice	Reproductive issues
47. <i>Ximenia americana</i>	Yellow plum	Olacaceae	Hemorrhoids leprosy	Fruit and seed contain hydrocyanic acid
48. <i>Yucca gloriosa</i>	Joshua tree	Liliaceae	Gout joint pain	hemolysis
49. <i>Ziziphus jujuba</i>	Jujube	Rhamnaceae	Liver disorder	Lower blood sugar level
50. <i>Zingiber officinalies</i>	Ginger	Zingiberaceae	Menstrual cramps	Skin irritation

Treatment

Pre hepatic jaundice

- Infusion of immunoglobulins is used as primary therapy for pre hepatic jaundice

- Alcohol hepatitis focuses on stopping alcohol use
- The viral hepatitis, antiviral are favoured for treatment of pre hepatic jaundice.

- The metallo porphyrin target the heme oxygenase enzyme to limit the production of bilirubin. (18)
- Ursodeoxycholic acid can decrease the production of gall stones by eliminate some bile acid
- Surgery or endoscopic procedures are used to release the obstruction
- Phototherapy is used for the treatment of high level of bilirubin i pre hepatic jaundice. (19)

Hepatic jaundice (20) (21)

- Antiviral medication and steroids are used to treat hepatocellular jaundice.
- Phototherapy and phenobarbital can be used for the therapy of neonatal jaundice.
- Cholestyramine can be prescribed to release the bile acids from the body
- Steroids and immunosuppressants used for the treatment of autoimmune hepatitis.
- Alcohol abstinence is the treatment for hepatic jaundice

Post hepatic jaundice

- Low fat diet should be given when the patient suffering from post hepatic jaundice.
- Cholestyramine use to release the bile acid from the body.
- Decompression can be done by surgical bypass used for the therapy of post hepatic jaundice.
- Phototherapy is used a special light to disintegrate the bilirubin so it can be easily removed from the body guard, but it not effective in adults (22)
- Naltrexone are used for the treatment of post hepatic jaundice(23)

CONCLUSION:

There are three types of jaundice: prehepatic, hepatic, and posthepatic. Jaundice is defined by yellowing of the skin and eyes as a result of high bilirubin levels. A comprehensive grasp of the pathogenesis, which can include bile duct blockages, liver dysfunction, or hemolytic diseases, is necessary for effective care. Physical examinations, blood testing, and imaging investigations are frequently used in the diagnosis process. The course of treatment for each condition is different and may include immunoglobulin infusion, antiviral drugs, dietary modifications, and, in certain situations, surgery. In order to improve patient outcomes and avoid complications related to this illness, awareness and prompt action are crucial.

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